

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Third Order Interaction Coefficients

K. M. Jha

Phenomenological equations in irreversible processes such as transport of matter through membranes under applied pressure or potential gradient has attracted the attention of several workers^{1,2}. The nature of these equations has been studied in detail in chemical reactions³. Interest has recently developed in the study of second and higher order interaction coefficients in transport processes. The dependence of the flow rate of matter on second order interaction coefficient, L_{112} , in electro-osmosis of acetone has been already reported⁴. The present note aims at suggesting an analytical method for the evaluation of the third order interaction coefficients from the data on electro-osmosis of a substance through membranes.

The phenomenological relation between volume flow rate of matter, J , pressure difference, ΔP , and potential difference, $\Delta \phi$, can be written⁴⁻⁶ as

$$J = L_{11} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right) + L_{12} \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right) + L_{111} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right)^2 + L_{112} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right) \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right) + L_{122} \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right)^2 + L_{1111} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right)^3 + L_{1112} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right) + L_{1122} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right) \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right)^2 + L_{1222} \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right)^3 + \dots \quad (1)$$

where L_{ik} ($i, k=1, 2$), L_{ijk} ($i, k, j=1, 2$) and L_{ijkl} ($i, k, j, l=1, 2$)

are the phenomenological coefficients. The latter two are the second and the third order rate constants. Consequently, the solvodynamic permeation and electro-osmotic permeation in the non-linear region would be given by

$$(J)_{\Delta \phi=0} = L_{11} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right) + L_{111} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right)^2 + L_{1111} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T} \right)^3 + \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } (J)_{\Delta P=0} = L_{12} \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right) + L_{122} \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right)^2 + L_{1222} \left(\frac{\Delta \phi}{T} \right)^3 + \dots \quad (3)$$

Since Poyseuille's law and Ohm's law are valid for fairly high values of ΔP and $\Delta \phi$ respectively hence L_{111} and L_{1111} , and L_{1112} , L_{1111} etc. would be zero for these values of ΔP

1. R. P. Rastogi and K. M. Jha; *J. Phys. Chem.*; 1966, 70, 1017-24.
2. R. P. Rastogi and K. M. Jha; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*; 1966, 62, 585-94.
3. R. P. Rastogi, R. C. Srivastava and K. Singh; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*; 1965, 61, 854-60.
4. J. C. M. Li; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 1414.
5. I Gyarmati; *Periodica Polytechnica (Hungary)*, 1961, 5, 219, 321.
6. P. Van Rysselberghe; *J. Chem. Phys.*; 1962, 36, 1327.

and $\Delta\phi$. Recent experiments on electro-osmosis of acetone⁸ has supported this argument. Further it has been shown conclusively that in the range of investigation up to 400 volts the total rate of permeation, i.e., $(J)_{\text{total}}$ is governed by the equation⁸

$$(J)_{\text{total}} = (J)_{\Delta\phi=0} + (J)_{\Delta P=0} + L_{111} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T}\right) \left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{T}\right) \quad \dots (4)$$

The order and magnitude of the second order interaction coefficient has been evaluated to be $(17 \pm 8.5) \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ } ^\circ\text{K}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1}$ on statistical considerations. The rate of electro-osmotic permeability of acetone has been found to be linear up to 440 volts i.e., L_{11}/T has been found to be independent of $\Delta\phi$ in this region. If the electro-osmotic flow measurements could be continued for higher values of $\Delta\phi$ where Ohm's law could still hold good and Poiseuille's law would be valid for the electro-osmotic pressure developed at those values of $\Delta\phi$, equation (1) under these conditions may be transformed to give

$$\frac{\{(J)_{\text{total}} - (J)_{\Delta\phi=0}\}}{\Delta\phi} = \frac{L_{11}}{T} + \frac{L_{111}}{T} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T}\right) + \frac{L_{1111}}{T} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T}\right)^2 + \frac{L_{1112}}{T} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T}\right) \left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{T}\right) + \dots (5)$$

$$\text{Or, } \frac{[(J)_{\text{total}} - \{(J)_{\Delta\phi=0} + (J)_{\Delta P=0}\}]}{\Delta\phi \Delta P} = \frac{L_{112}}{T^2} + \frac{L_{1111}}{T^3} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{T}\right) + \frac{L_{1122}}{T^3} \left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{T}\right) + \dots (6)$$

The value of each quantity in the parenthesis of the R.H.S. can be experimentally determined for any value of ΔP and $\Delta\phi$. The value thus obtained for different values of $\Delta\phi$ at any fixed and constant value of ΔP at constant temperature may be plotted against $\Delta\phi$. As evident from equation (6) we should get a straight line the slope of which would give the value of L_{112}/T^3 and the intercept would be equal to $L_{112}/T^3 + L_{1111}/T^3 \Delta P$. Since ΔP is constant and L_{112}/T^3 can be evaluated from the experiment⁸ L_{1111}/T^3 can well be evaluated. These in turn would give L_{112} and L_{111} as T is constant and known.